

Freddy Castillo <fcastillo.alfonso@gmail.com>

Genome submission SUB15698091, "Genome_corrected_final.sqn genome submission"

2 mensajes

genomes@ncbi.nlm.nih.gov <genomes@ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>
Para: fcastillo.alfonso@gmail.com

13 de octubre de 2025, 14:00

Dear Freddy Castillo-Alfonso,

Annual funding for much of the federal government expired at 11:59 pm ET on Tuesday, September 30, 2025. As a result, certain federal government activities have ceased due to lack of appropriated funding, because of a lapse in government funding, the agency may not be able to respond to inquiries until appropriations are enacted. Updates regarding government operating status and resumption of normal operations can be found at opm.gov.

This is an automatic acknowledgment that genome accession(s) have been assigned to your submission SUB15698091, "Genome_corrected_final.sqn genome submission", accession number JBNIIW000000000. Before being released, the genome will be manually reviewed by our indexing staff to be sure that there are no remaining errors or problems. We will contact you if we have any questions. Note that genomes remain at the 'processing' stage until they have been made public.

Sincerely,
NCBI GenBank Staff

Freddy Castillo <fcastillo.alfonso@gmail.com>
Para: Cristal Zuniga <czuniga2@sdsu.edu>

21 de octubre de 2025, 19:16

Mtro. Freddy Castillo Alfonso
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